

Impact of School Disciplinary Practices on the Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students

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Abstract

School disciplinary practices play a vital role in enhancing the academic achievement of secondary school students. This research primarily focuses on identifying the impact of school disciplinary practices on the learning outcomes of senior secondary students within the Tamil medium schools of the Passara Educational Zone. The study was structured to explore the relationship between discipline and academic success, evaluate the contribution of disciplinary measures to educational activities, and analyze their influence on the social habits and personality development of students. Using a mixed-method research design, data were collected from 60 teachers, 6 principals, and 6 deputy principals through structured questionnaires and interviews. Quantitative data were processed using SPSS software, while qualitative insights were analyzed through thematic analysis. The findings indicate that effective disciplinary practices foster positive outcomes, including strengthened teacher-student relationships, enhanced responsibility, better time management, and the development of leadership qualities and self-confidence. Notably, 90% of the surveyed teachers agreed that consistent disciplinary procedures significantly improve student learning achievement. However, the study also identified that severe punishments, partiality in enforcement, and a failure to consider students' psychological well-being can lead to negative educational consequences. Furthermore, the results emphasize that the collaboration of parents with school administrators and teachers is crucial for maintaining effective discipline. Consequently, the research suggests that disciplinary practices should be guidance-oriented, impartial, and supportive rather than purely punitive. These findings are expected to assist educational administrators and school heads in restructuring disciplinary frameworks to better support the holistic development and

academic excellence of secondary school students.

Keywords:

Junior secondary level students, disciplinary practices, academic achievement

1.0 Introduction

In today's educational environment, students' learning achievement is influenced by various factors. In particular, the disciplinary rules and disciplinary activities implemented in schools play a vital role in students' educational progress. These help in creating an optimal learning environment and in controlling the behavioral patterns of students.

The secondary school stage is considered a very important phase in the scientific, emotional, and social development of students. At this level, variations can be observed in students' educational achievement, classroom attendance, and subject engagement based on how they approach disciplinary rules.

School discipline plays an unavoidable role in educational progress. A school that fails to demonstrate progress in student discipline cannot take pride in any other form of progress. To that extent, the concept of education is found to be intertwined with student discipline. For a student's future to be successful, discipline must be taught alongside the necessary education. In this regard, the contribution of parents is just as important as that of teachers. Furthermore, this research will help to clearly understand whether disciplinary procedures act as a favorable factor or a negative impact on students' educational progress.

In this context, this study has been conducted with the aim of analyzing the impact of school disciplinary procedures on the learning achievement of secondary school students, based on four schools in the Passara Division of the Badulla District.

2.0 Research Background

Discipline is a cultural value that enriches individual and social lives and makes them meaningful. It is essential for every human being to possess individual values such as love, courage, discipline, integrity, and tolerance. However, in today's modern world, profound changes can be observed due to the excessive growth of technology.

In this context, the impact of school disciplinary procedures on the academic achievement of secondary school students has emerged as a significant aspect of educational research. The secondary school stage is regarded as the most critical period of a student's life. To reinforce this view, Steinberg (2011) defines the "secondary stage" in his study as a period characterized by magnificent changes. He points out that this is the stage where students' academic performance, character, and discipline are formed. Accordingly, schools serve as the primary place where students acquire the necessary qualities and discipline for life, in addition to formal education.

Wijesinghe (2015) explains the secondary stage development of Sri Lankan students. He specifically notes that students from plantation areas are currently passing through an identity-formation period, seeking answers to questions such as "Who am I?" and "What is the purpose of my life?". In this regard, this research is being conducted to investigate how school disciplinary procedures bring about changes among secondary school students in the Passara Division of the Badulla District.

While school principals ensure the implementation of disciplinary activities to create a conducive learning environment, researchers in recent times have identified that poor academic achievement among students is often caused by a lack of discipline. Studies conducted on children and school students show that disciplinary issues result in lower academic performance. Specifically, in an educational environment where disciplinary problems are high, students become unable to increase their own potential (Skiba et al., 2011). This study investigates whether the undisciplined actions of school students disrupt learning and have a direct impact on their achievements.

Because behavioral misconduct, including substance abuse from society, is being transmitted to students at a high level, it is

essential to create awareness among today's students—who are to become tomorrow's leaders, professionals, and pioneers of the nation—to prevent them from gambling away their lives for petty pleasures. Furthermore, some studies have explored the consequences of mandatory disciplinary actions and student interest. This, in reality, points toward errors in the learning process if disciplinary problems are not corrected (Macswan & Rolstad, 2003). In this regard, Badulla is an area belonging to the hill country. Due to the lack of adherence to school disciplinary procedures in Passara Division schools, students are being temporarily suspended or are transferring to other schools. Female students, as a result of their behavioral misconduct, lose their school education and find their lives diverted toward issues like early marriage.

Gunawardana (2018) points out in his research that early marriages are more prevalent in plantation areas compared to other regions of Sri Lanka, citing lack of education, economic poverty, social traditions, and lack of proper protection for women as the primary factors.

Because parents in these regions lack sufficient educational and technological knowledge to remain vigilant about the internet sites that today's generation prefers to use, it creates a situation that students exploit, leading to the misuse of technology. Consequently, children's engagement in learning is decreasing. According to the research of Perera & Fernando (2020), more than 60% of students aged 13–17 in Sri Lanka, especially in urban areas, spend more than 4 hours daily on the internet. This affects not only their educational performance but also their disciplinary behavior.

Furthermore, as a child's engagement in learning decreases, their level of academic achievement is also severely affected. It is the duty of the school to eliminate students' disciplinary problems and transform them into good citizens acceptable to society. By identifying the causes of disciplinary value issues and providing proper counseling at the school level, student engagement in learning and their achievements must be improved. Therefore, it is highly essential for all students attending school to be liberated from disciplinary problems to achieve the appropriate levels of competency and learning outcomes. This study was undertaken based on these backgrounds.

3.0 Research Problem

Problems arising within the field of education affect not only the students but also the society that depends on them. If a student lacks discipline, their Education becomes like “bookish knowledge of a gourd” (a Tamil proverb meaning Purely theoretical and impractical), proving to be entirely useless.

Due to the changes over time, the basic structures of society have transformed. Technological growth, media, and modern facilities, including the internet, are creating significant impacts on student discipline (Subramaniyan, 2020).

It is a notable point that while students have achieved intellectual growth due to the monstrous advancement of technology, their moral characteristics are simultaneously declining. When utilizing technology, students must learn digital etiquette, responsible behavior, and online ethics. In the absence of such education, disciplinary lapses will increase (Ribble, 2011).

A study conducted by Erica et al. (2019) regarding disciplinary procedures examined how school policies provide solutions to students' disciplinary problems. It found that matters related to justice within school policies have a deep impact on students' feelings; when students feel dissatisfied, it creates opportunities for them to engage in misconduct or criminal acts. Therefore, these researchers state that if harsh elements like punishment and suspension are removed from school policies and replaced with methods that encourage accountability and student trust, student offenses will decrease, and the school environment will improve.

The research by Raden & Ati Sumiati (2023) examined the differences caused by school and family environments (surroundings and events) on students' disciplinary practices. This research concluded that the correlation between family environment and student discipline is 17%, while the correlation between school environment and student discipline is 30%. It also noted that when both the family and school environments act simultaneously, they maintain a 32% positive correlation with student discipline.

In a study regarding the impact of the social environment on student behavior, the changes in students' disciplinary problems caused by the effects of social media were analyzed (Kenen & Ercetin, 2014). It found that social

media can have both positive and negative effects on student discipline. Therefore, it was researched that disciplinary problems can be reduced by recommending and implementing ways to use social media in a manner compatible with education.

Furthermore, Wijesinghe (2021) noted in his research that changes in educational Systems, a competitive mindset, and curriculum pressure subject students to mental stress, which in turn causes changes in their discipline.

Although research has been conducted regarding the aforementioned disciplinary procedures, information regarding modern problems could not be obtained from those studies. Moreover, the specific impact that disciplinary procedures have on learning achievement has not been sufficiently explored. An academic review by the Intercultural Development Research Association (2020) points out that exclusionary disciplinary actions decrease students' academic achievement and increase school dropout rates.

Most existing studies are centered on foreign countries and have been researched according to their specific environments. For example, researchers like Erica et Al. (2019), Gouda & Laveena (2019), Raden & Ati Sumiati (2023), and Kenen & Ercetin (2014) are foreigners, and their studies are focused on their respective countries. Therefore, it is essential in the current context to conduct a study to evaluate the impact of school disciplinary procedures on the learning Achievement of secondary school students in our country.

Accordingly, this research was undertaken with the aim of evaluating the impact of school disciplinary procedures on the learning achievement of secondary School students in the Passara Division of the Badulla District, using Tamil Medium schools as the basis.

4.0 Literature Review

The literature review serves to enrich the research and identify variables by drawing knowledge and insights from primary theories and past studies. It also helps to verify whether the research findings align with the results of other researchers (Kalamani, 2014).

Senior secondary students are generally between the ages of 13 and 16. During this period, their physical, emotional, and social development increases. This Stage,

characterized by a majestic state of mind, social relationships, and the search for identity, is known as adolescence (Santrock, 2018). Senior secondary education acts as a critical bridge, preparing students for higher education or Employment; here, students explore specialized subjects and develop deep learning skills (OECD, 2018).

Students at this stage require psychological support to enhance their Self-esteem, cope with social pressures, and develop meaningful relationships (Steinberg, 2014). How young people anticipate and create their future employment opportunities is a multi-dimensional and multi-stage process. Studies have shown that how they view their future work is significantly influenced by their specific environment. While most research in this area has been conducted with youth from western cultures, a study of senior high school students in Romania investigated the relationship between individual or social factors, family, peers, and social support in future job planning (Lovu, 2013).

Disciplinary procedures should be designed with the aim of fostering Self-discipline in students. They represent planned actions taken by teachers and administrators to prevent negative behavior and create an orderly learning environment (Bear, 2010). Activities based on “Zero Tolerance” policies and early identification should be implemented in schools (Skiba & Peterson, 2000).

Through the approach known as Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports (PBIS), disciplinary procedures are structured in a positive manner (Sugai & Horner, 2006). Disciplinary activities in schools are directly related to Students’ educational success; disciplinary discrimination is directly linked to educational discrimination. When disciplinary procedures are implemented in an organized and smooth manner, students perceive a sense of justice, which creates a greater opportunity for them to engage in learning (Gregory et al., 2010).

Researchers have recently explored the disciplinary problems faced by teachers In Sri Lanka and the procedures followed (Ekanayake, 2013), as well as national and international procedures against corporal punishment (Perera, 2016). In Sri Lankan schools, disciplinary practices such as corporal punishment, shaming, and isolation are prevalent. These not only affect the mental

state of students but also reduce their educational enthusiasm (NCPA, 2017).

Ethics (or discipline) is the science that studies human behavior in society. When all humans achieve fulfillment in their basic needs—food, clothing, and shelter—and lead a satisfied, organized social life, discipline reaches its Fulfillment (Shanmuganathan, 2014). In schools, discipline has historically been Emphasized to build perfect disciplinary procedures. In the past, discipline was considered as students’ obedience to the teacher’s word. Discipline was built by preventing students’ deviant behaviors through punishments such as canning, making them stand on their knees, or slapping them on the head (Nespur, 2013).

The study by Thapa (2013) investigates the direct empirical relationships between disciplinary repositories, student discipline, and social activities. It mathematically supports that in a school environment, students’ behavior, discipline, and cooperation skills improve through social-emotional learning.

In Sri Lanka, the relationship between the educational environment, social unity, and discipline is depicted with empirical data. That is, the school environment is a social structure, and student discipline and social unity are elements that can be created by the educational environment. Specifically, in Sri Lanka’s diverse social environment, education serves as an important medium for improving discipline and fostering social unity (Jeyaweera, 2010).

One must examine the role of the school environment in shaping the social behaviors of adolescents. It focuses on the importance of peer influence and teacher-student relationships as key components affecting social adjustment. The study reveals that physical aspects of the school environment, such as classroom design and safety measures, are vital for fostering a sense of belonging and safety; this supports social adjustment. Peer relationships are identified as a significant factor; positive relationships improve social skills and empathy, while negative relationships contribute to behavioral problems. Additionally, the quality of teacher-student relationships plays a key role in affecting social behaviors; supportive and respectful relationships lead to better social skills. Findings highlight the importance of

creating a supportive school environment to encourage positive social development among secondary school students. This study provides practical insights for educators, policymakers, and administrators to improve school environments and enhance social outcomes for youth (Kumari & Biswas, 2023).

A study on the impact of students' disciplinary problems on efficient learning indirectly points out that mental health issues can be a cause. Psychological complications can affect learning achievement and lead to undisciplined behavior (Dilani, 2017). It mentions that negative emotions such as anger, anxiety, jealousy, and fighting are found among senior secondary students, and these affect learning. These emotions are student-related factors that lead to a lack of discipline (Dakshayini, 2016). It speaks about changes occurring in brain development, risky decision-making, and self-control in growing adolescents. It explains how these changes impact students' behavior and disciplinary decisions (Steinberg, 2014).

Self-discipline is important not only for learning but also for behavioral control. Students with self-control deficiencies may struggle to follow disciplinary rules (Zimmerman, 2000). It speaks about the importance and impact of peer relationships among growing adolescents. It investigates how peer influence, especially in risky behaviors, acts as a trigger (Brown & Larson, 2009). It has been found that peer pressure creates a significant impact on students' undisciplined behavior (Owuor, 2020).

Studies point out that schools without adequate resources for students coming from low socio-economic backgrounds may increase disciplinary problems. Sufficient teacher-student ratios, supportive staff, and learning resources help improve disciplinary behavior (Lee & Burkam, 2002). The way school management involves parents and society in students' education and disciplinary development also affects student behavior. Strong parent-school relationships, the functioning of Parent-Teacher Associations, and the utilization of social resources provide the necessary support for students' disciplinary behavior. Parents' involvement in their children's school activities increases responsibility and obedience to school rules among students (Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

It investigates how family activities, such as mutual relationships among family members,

conflict resolution, communication, and family stability, impact children's social-emotional development. Strong, supportive family activities have been found to develop children's emotional regulation, empathy, and positive social behavior. This indirectly leads to disciplined behavior. Problems, conflicts, or disruptions within the family can be the cause of children's behavioral problems (Feinberg, 2018). It explores in detail how parental supervision and control help reduce adolescents' risky behaviors (alcohol habit, substance use, anti-social acts) and lack of discipline. Researching studies with various cultural and social backgrounds after 2015, it was found that appropriate supervision combined with open communication develops responsible decision-making skills among adolescents and encourages disciplined behavior (Laird & Deater-Deckard, 2016).

It investigates how the family's Socio-Economic Status (SES) and the mental stress faced by parents affect children's behavior and discipline. It points out that low SES and high parental stress can create challenges in parenting methods, leading to children's behavior and disciplinary problems. However, it also emphasizes the importance of family support programs to reduce the impact of these factors (Yoshikawa, 2015).

A school's disciplinary environment (school climate) creates a direct impact on student enthusiasm, attendance, and educational cycles. A positive disciplinary environment makes students feel safe and respected (Thapa et al., 2013). Disciplinary gaps often lead to achievement gaps. Specifically, procedures such as excessive punishment or exclusion led to academic backwardness by distancing students from the classroom (Gregory et al., 2010).

It provides insights into how a school's culture affects its disciplinary procedures, students' behavior, students' learning achievement, and the overall educational environment. It illustrates that a strong, positive culture naturally encourages discipline (Schein, 2010). It provides research-based strategies for managing discipline efficiently in the classroom. It shows how learning achievements can be improved by teachers setting clear expectations, following consistent rules, and creating a supportive environment for students (Marzano, Marzano & Pickering, 2003).

This study investigates the disciplinary methods used by teachers in Sri Lankan Schools. It found that teachers widely use physical punishments and psychological violence. It is mentioned that 80.4% of students experienced Physical punishment at least once, and 72.5% experienced psychological violence. At the same time, although positive disciplinary procedures were used, they were Less frequent than negative methods. This study emphasizes that such punishments Can have a negative impact on students' educational achievement and highlights the necessity of alternative approaches (De Zoysa, Senarath & De Silva, 2018).

This study investigated the knowledge, practice, and opinions of Jaffna Educational zone teachers regarding physical punishment. It reveals that a significant number of teachers still use physical punishment as a disciplinary Strategy and that there is a lack of sufficient training regarding positive Disciplinary procedures. This can be detrimental to students' education and psychological development (Mayoran et al., 2023).

This report on UNICEF Sri Lanka's initiatives shows how a happy learning Experience can be created for students by introducing positive disciplinary Procedures as an alternative to physical punishment. In some schools, teachers Trained in positive discipline have observed better engagement among students and improvement in teacher-student relationships. This creates a favorable Impact on students' learning achievement (UNICEF, 2023).

This article cites some incidents of students committing suicide due to Discipline-related problems in Sri Lankan schools. This illustrates the severe Negative consequences that disciplinary procedures can have on students' mental State (Daily Mirror, 2014).

Loneliness (30.8%), anxiety (20.2%), and suicidal ideation (3.7%) are found to Be prevalent among Sri Lankan school students. This study recommends that Improving positive home and school environments will help reduce students' Mental health problems (Rasalingam et al., 2022).

In Sri Lankan initiatives, teachers trained in positive discipline have observed better engagement among students and progress in teacher-student relationships. Such approaches not only improve the mental state of students

but also create a Happy learning environment. It has been found that 80.4% of students in Sri Lankan schools have experienced physical punishment at least once. This causes psychological distress among students and long-term psychological impacts (UNICEF, 2023).

Marzano & Marzano (2003) state that when organized disciplinary procedures Prevail in the classroom, the student's attention cycle increases, and in the long term, the graduation rate rises. Bear (2010) explains that controlled Disciplinary procedures encourage mental health benefits such as a sense of Safety, trust, and social cooperation in students. In the Ministry of Education, Sri Lanka (2021) "Whole School Development" report, it is stated that if Disciplinary procedures are not planned and implemented, educational activities Such as honesty, responsibility, and cooperation among students will be affected. The study by Lewis (2001) notes that when students perceive disciplinary procedures as fair, Improvement is seen in their classroom behavior and educational performance.

5.0 Research Objectives

1. To identify the relationship between school disciplinary practices and Students' academic achievement.
2. To identify the contribution of disciplinary practices to the learning Activities of senior secondary students.
3. To analyze the positive and negative impacts of school disciplinary Practices on academic achievement.
4. To evaluate the impact of disciplinary practices on the social habits and Personality development of secondary school students.

6.0 Research Methodology

6.1 Research Method

This study utilizes quantitative measurement methods by using marks/grades to understand students' academic achievement. Simultaneously, qualitative methods are employed to capture the impact of student discipline, as well as their feelings and experiences.

Therefore, since this study utilizes both quantitative and qualitative data, it is designed as Mixed Methods research. This approach is appropriate as data is Collected through both questionnaires and interviews. According to Creswell (2014), quantitative data and

qualitative data can be integrated within a single Study using mixed methods.

Primary data for this study was collected from teachers working in Tamil-medium Schools in the Passara Educational Zone of the Badulla District through Structured questionnaires. Additionally, information was obtained from Principals and students through the interview method. Utilizing a mixed-methods Approach allowed for the impact of school disciplinary

procedures on student Achievement to be analyzed both numerically and descriptively, ensuring the Research progressed effectively.

6.2 Population

The population for this study consists of 60 teachers teaching grades 9 to 11, 06 principals, and 06 vice-principals from Tamil-medium schools in the Passara Educational Zone of the Badulla District.

No	School	Type	Principals	Vice-Principals	Teachers
1	A	1 C	1	1	10
2	B	TYPE 2	1	1	08
3	C	1 AB	1	1	24
4	D	1 C	1	1	10
5	E	TYPE 2	1	1	7
6	F	1C	1	1	12

6.3 Research Sample Selection

Teachers were considered the primary respondents for this study. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan table, 60 teachers who teach grades 9 to 11 were selected as the research sample using the random sampling method. Additionally, 12 Individuals (principals and vice-principals) were selected through convenience Sampling for data collection via interviews.

6.4 Data Analysis Method

Data analysis serves as a preliminary step toward obtaining the research Results. It is essential to analyze the data collected through research tools to Find solutions to the research problems and to determine if the collected data Sufficiently highlights the issues.

- Part 1: Basic questions were compiled and analyzed using frequency tables.

- Part 2: Descriptive statistical analysis was used to identify the type of Impact school disciplinary procedures have on students' academic Achievement.

- Part 3: Thematic analysis was used to analyze how disciplinary procedures Contribute to the educational activities of secondary students.

- Part 4: Descriptive analysis was used to explore the positive and negative Consequences of school disciplinary procedures on academic achievement.

- Part 5: Descriptive analysis was used to evaluate the impact of disciplinary Procedures on the social habits and personality development of secondary School students.

6.5 Data Analysis Techniques based on Research Objectives

Questions	Tools	Nature of Data	Analysis Technique
Basic Information	Teacher Questionnaire	Quantitative	Frequency Table
Impact of disciplinary procedures on learning achievement	Teacher Questionnaire	Quantitative	Descriptive Statistics

Contribution of discipline to educational activities	Teacher Questionnaire, Disciplinary Records, Principal Interviews	Quantitative Qualitative	Descriptive Statistics Thematic Analysis
Positive and negative consequences on achievement	Teacher Questionnaire> Principal Interviews	Quantitative Qualitative	Descriptive Statistics
Impact on social habits and personality development	Teacher Questionnaire> Principal Interviews	Quantitative Qualitative	Descriptive Statistics Thematic Analysis

7.0 Findings And Results

Based on the analysis conducted in Chapter 4, the following findings are summarized from the questionnaires collected from 60 teachers and interviews conducted with 6 principals and 6 vice-principals across 6 schools.

1. General Information (Demographics)

- Gender: Of the 60 teachers, 75.0% (45) were female and 25.0% (15) were male. This indicates the findings largely reflect the perspectives of female teachers.
- Class Size: 79.0% (42) of teachers manage classrooms with 11–20 or 21–30 students. The data is thus based on the experience of teachers handling significant student numbers.
- Teacher Qualifications: 63.4% (38) are trained teachers from National Colleges of Education or Teacher Training Colleges. This adds strength to the research as the responses come from professionally qualified individuals.
- Service Experience: 43.3% of the participants have 6–10 years of teaching experience.

2. Relationship Between School Discipline and Achievement (Objective 1)

- Clarity of Rules: 81.7% of teachers agreed that school disciplinary procedures are clearly defined. This was corroborated by principals during Interviews.
- Impact on Achievement: 95% of teachers confirmed that students who follow school disciplinary procedures show improved academic achievement.
- Lack of Progress: 69.9% of teachers agreed that the academic achievement of students

who do not follow disciplinary procedures does not improve.

- Necessity of Discipline: 96.7% of teachers stated that following disciplinary procedures is essential for improving student learning achievement.
- Administrative Perspective: During interviews, a majority stated that a disciplined environment increases student attention and engagement. It fosters qualities like time management and responsibility. They noted that counseling-based procedures, rather than punishment, change student mindsets and reduce mental stress.
- Special Programs: Interviews revealed that schools implement programs such as monitoring student attendance, allocating time for counseling sessions, and providing rewards for students who demonstrate excellent behavior.

3. Discipline in Educational Activities (Objective 2)

- Support for Progress: The factor that disciplinary procedures support students' educational progress received a very high mean score of 4.5167.
- Successful Instruction: Teachers strongly believe (mean: 4.5000) that classroom educational activities can be carried out successfully when students follow disciplinary rules, as it prevents disruptions.
- Student Interest: There is a clear consensus (mean: 4.3667) that following disciplinary procedures increases students' enthusiasm for learning.

- Current Status: Teachers gave a mean value of 3.7667 for the statement that disciplinary procedures are correctly followed in schools, but gave a lower value of 3.5500 for the statement that the majority of students actually adhere to these rules.

4. Positive and Negative Impacts of Discipline (Objective 3)

- Handling Rule Violations: Principals reported that when rules are broken, they do not immediately resort to punishment. Instead, they follow a step-by-step process: questioning the student, giving a warning, providing advice, approaching parents, and referring the student to the disciplinary committee/counseling.
- Positive Outcomes: These approaches strengthen the teacher-student relationship, provide opportunities for students to correct their mistakes, and allow for continuous monitoring. The fear of a bad reputation reaching parents often acts as a deterrent for students.
- Classroom Environment: Strict discipline creates at least a temporary silence, making it easier to conduct lessons.

5. The Role of Parents

Interviews emphasized that parental contribution is vital for solving disciplinary problems. For discipline to be lifelong, parents must be involved. Parents' own behavior, their way of speaking, and their level of control directly impact the student's behavior in school. Schools engage parents through Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings, term-end result discussions, and involving them in school volunteer work (shramadana).

6. Social Habits and Personality Development (Objective 4)

- Social Qualities: Over 95% of teachers agreed (with mean scores between 4.2 and 4.6) that following school discipline helps students develop healthy peer relationships, leadership qualities, teamwork skills, respect for elders, and social responsibility.
- Personality Development: Adolescence is the most important stage for personality formation. Teachers noted that self-control, time management, responsibility, respect, self-confidence, self-worth, and decision-making skills are significantly influenced by the disciplinary environment.

8.0 Research Conclusions

The following conclusions were reached based on the data analysis and Discussions conducted in the Tamil-medium schools of the Passara Educational Zone:

- The study reveals that in schools where disciplinary rules are implemented clearly and consistently, the academic achievement of secondary school students improves. This leads to the conclusion that there is a significant positive relationship between school disciplinary procedures and student academic achievement.
 - The research found that providing priority to counseling, guidance, and encouragement has a much greater impact on students' learning achievement than prioritizing punishment. Therefore, it is concluded that disciplinary procedures based on guidance and counseling yield the most benefit.
 - Severe physical or psychological punishments were found to create fear and mental stress among students, fostering a negative attitude toward the school and ultimately hindering their academic achievement. Thus, it can be concluded that harsh punitive methods lead to negative consequences.
 - When teachers understand their students and approach them with kindness and empathy, students follow disciplinary procedures more effectively, which in turn elevates their interest in learning and their academic results. Disciplinary procedures serve as a helpful tool in effectively managing the teacher-student relationship.
- Overall Conclusion: The final conclusion of this research is that when school disciplinary procedures are clearly formulated and students are encouraged to follow them correctly, they engage more effectively in learning alongside their disciplined behavior, resulting in enhanced academic achievement.

9.0 References

- Arcia, E. (2006). Achievement and enrollment status of suspended students: Outcomes in a large, multicultural school district. *Education and Urban Society*, 38(3), 359–369.
- Bear, G. G. (2010). *School discipline and self-discipline: A practical guide to promoting prosocial student behavior*. Guilford Press.
- Birch, S. H., & Ladd, G. W. (1997). The teacher-child relationship and children's early

- school adjustment. *Journal of School Psychology*, 35(1), 61-79.
- Bradshaw, C. P., Mitchell, M. M., & Leaf, P. J. (2010). Examining the effects of schoolwide positive behavioral interventions and supports on student outcomes. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 12(3), 133–148.
- Brand, S., Felner, R. D., Shim, M., Seitsinger, A., & Dumas, T. (2003). Middle school improvement and reform: Development and validation of a school-level assessment of climate, cultural pluralism, and school safety. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(3), 570–588.
- Brew, E. A., Nketiah, B., & Koranteng, R. (2021). A literature review of academic performance, an insight into factors and their influences on academic outcomes of students at senior high schools. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8, <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1107423>
- Brown, B. B., & Larson, R. W. (Eds.). (2009). *The world's youth: Adolescence in eight regions of the globe*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, J., McCabe, L., Michelli, N. M., & Pickeral, T. (2009). School climate: Research, policy, practice, and teacher education. *Teachers College Record*, 111(1), 180-213.
- De Silva, I. W. (2015). Fear and discipline in Sri Lankan schools: A sociological perspective. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies*, 7(1), 24–39.
- Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405–432.
- Eccles, J. S., & Roeser, R. W. (2011). Schools as developmental contexts during adolescence. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 21(1), 225–241.
- Ekanayake, S. B. (2013). Managing student discipline in Sri Lankan schools: Challenges and practices. *Sri Lanka Journal of Education Research*, 1(2), 45–60.
- Elias, M. J., Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Frey, K. S., Greenberg, M. T., Haynes, N. M., ... & Shriver, T. P. (1997). Promoting social and emotional learning: Guidelines for educators. *ASCD*.
- Erikson, E. H. (1968). *Identity: Youth and crisis*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Feinberg, M. E., Jones, D. E., & Kan, M. L. (2018). The effects of family structure on the development of children's social-emotional competence: A systematic review. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 27(11), 3740-3760.
- Gregory, A., Skiba, R. J., & Noguera, P. A. (2010). The achievement gap and the discipline gap: Two sides of the same coin? *Educational Researcher*, 39(1), 59–68.
- Hammerfelt, B. (2019). Discipline, *ISKO encyclopedia of knowledge organization*.
- Harter, S. (1999). *The construction of the self: A developmental perspective*. Guilford Press.
- Henderson, A. T., & Mapp, K. L. (2002). A new wave of evidence: The impact of school, family, and community connections on student achievement. *National Center for Family & Community Connections with Schools*.
- UNICEF Sri Lanka. (2019). *Child-Friendly Schools and Corporal Punishment in Sri Lanka: A situational analysis*. Colombo: UNICEF Sri Lanka.
- Welsh, R. O., Little, S. (2018). The school discipline dilemma: A comprehensive review of disparities and alternative approaches, *Review of Educational Research*, 88(5), 752-794.
- Yoshikawa, H., Aber, J. L., & Beardslee, W. R. (2015). The effects of poverty on the developing brain and the role of protective factors. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 11, 1-28.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). Attaining self-regulation: A social cognitive perspective. In M. Boekaerts, P. R. Pintrich, & M. Zeidner (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation* (pp. 13-39). Academic Press.